

TOUGHNESS IN COMPOSITES: THE NEED TO CONSIDER

THE STRUCTURAL INTEGRITY

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The crack opening displacement needed to generate pull-out work appears to be much larger than the elastic crack opening at high stresses. The resultant large strains at the crack tip could therefore initiate cracks in the matrix there. The energetics of this process is investigated with the aid of a notional negative crack pressure, and it is shown that there is a danger of unstable propagation of cracks in the matrix. These cracks seem likely to be able to fracture the matrix completely when the toughening due to fibre pull-out is large, and the applied stress is greater than a quarter of the composite ultimate strength.

Introduction

Fibre pull-out has been recognized as an important contributor to toughness since the early days of the development of synthetic composites (1). It is not always necessary for the fibres to be short for pull-out to occur (2-4); in composites reinforced with low breaking strain, continuous, fibres (5), the fibres appear to break up, in the high stress field at the crack tip, into pieces of about the critical length for reinforcement. This leads to the happy result that the toughness is then as great as possible for any given fibre-matrix bond strength. This toughness seems to be obtained without any corresponding loss in other properties.

The toughness can apparently be still further increased by reducing the fibre-matrix bond strength (2), and this process can be extended indefinitely, by suitable choice of fibre and matrix (6). It has even been proposed that special spiral, or kinked fibres should be made which can be pulled out continuously to give what may appear to be an infinitely great work of fracture (7,8).

However, all methods of toughening using pull-out depend for their effectiveness on large crack opening displacements. These are undesirable, and can render a structure unserviceable when complete fracture failure has not occurred. An example of this is the fate of steel reinforced concrete lamp posts after impact by a vehicle. The concrete fractures, leaving the steel bridging the crack, but the crack opening displacement is so large that the post is prostrated.

A criterion which takes this into account was introduced in 1970 (6). This was subsequently labelled fracture "structural integrity" (9) and it was shown that toughening by maximizing stress relaxation and redistribution satisfies this criterion much better than toughening that relies on fibre pull-out. Continuous pull-out was found to be totally ineffective unless certain criteria, formerly unnoticed, were observed.

This paper examines the concept of fracture structural integrity in more detail, and attempts to determine the limits to the usefulness of fibre pull-out toughening.

Theory

Elastic Crack Opening

A vanishingly thin planar crack in an isotropic elastic body opens up and assumes an elliptic profile when the body is stressed (Figure 1a). The major axis of the ellipse has the length v_{\max} where

$$v_{\max} = \frac{(1+\nu) \sigma_c a_0}{4E} \quad (1)$$

In this equation σ_c is the applied stress, ν the Poisson's ratio, and E the Young's modulus of the material (10). $2a_0$ is the total crack length.

The expression for the elastic crack opening for highly anisotropic aligned fibre composites does not appear to have been derived. However, we can develop an expression for v_{\max} in terms of the work of fracture. This will not be strongly influenced by the elastic constants, and so should give a good indication of the value for the elastic crack opening for these composites.

The Griffith-Irwin equation (11) for isotropic materials in plane strain is

Fig. 1 Crack in an aligned short fibre composite. (a) elastic crack opening, (b) crack opening accompanied by fibre displacements in the matrix at the crack tip, (c) crack opening with additional matrix cracking.

$$\sigma_{cc}^2 = \frac{EG}{\pi(1-\nu^2)a_0} \quad (2)$$

Here, G is the work of fracture and σ_{cc} is the critical stress for fracture for a crack of length a_0 . Eliminating E between equations 1 and 2 we obtain

$$2\nu_{max} = \frac{G}{2\pi(1-\nu)\sigma_{cc}} \quad (3)$$

where $2\nu_{max}$ is now the elastic opening of crack subject to the critical stress for fracture.

Crack Opening Displacement (C.O.D.)

Wells (12) was one of the first people to recognize the importance of the C.O.D. in isotropic homogeneous materials. When a material is ductile, it yields in the highly stressed region at the tip of a crack, the crack opens up, and the tip becomes blunt. The analogous process in an aligned fibre composite is illustrated in Figure 1b. Here δ_p is the C.O.D.

The C.O.D. in such a composite can be calculated when the applied stress reaches the critical value for fracture. It will simply be half the fibre length, so long as this is not greater than the critical length for reinforcement, l_c .

We will consider a composite in which the toughness has been maximized by using fibres having the critical length. Then

$$\delta_p = l_c/2 = \sigma_{fu}d/4\tau \quad (4)$$

where σ_{fu} is the fibre strength, and d the fibre diameter. τ is the shear stress developed between the fibres and the matrix while pull-out is taking place. (Note that δ_p has the same value for some continuous fibre composites in which the fibres break up due to the local stresses at the crack tip (2).)

If we substitute for G in equation 3 the expression (9) for the work of fracture due to fibre pull-out:

$$G_{fp} = V_f d \sigma_{fu}^2 / 12\tau \quad (5)$$

where V_f is the fibre volume fraction, we can compare the values of $2\nu_{max}$ and δ_p . Thus we have

$$\frac{\delta_p}{2\nu_{max}} = \frac{6\pi(1-\nu)\sigma_{cc}}{V_f\sigma_{fu}}$$

For σ_{cc} close to $V_f\sigma_{fu}$, which is the approximate strength of a well reinforced polymer, this ratio can be quite large. For example, for $\sigma_{cc} = V_f\sigma_{fu}/2$ it is roughly equal to ten.

Process Zone

With large C.O.D.'s a corresponding large worked zone is to be expected at the crack tip (Figure 1b). This zone is observed as a whitish region close to the crack tip in reinforced polymers under stress (13). In metals this zone is called the process zone, and its extent can be roughly estimated (12) as r_p where

$$r_p = a_o \left(\frac{\sigma_c}{\sigma_y} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

where σ_y is the yield stress of the metal. This can be a significant fraction of the crack length when σ_c approaches σ_y .

In order to analyse the behaviour of cracks with significant process zones, a notional increase of crack length, equal to r_p , has been adopted (14). The anisotropy of composite materials renders this approach unsuitable. We will, instead, adopt a notional internal pressure in the crack. This may be justified because of the physical situation at the crack tip, and because an internal pressure is equivalent to a change in crack length.

We will examine the physical situation first. The large strains at the crack tip are likely to cause matrix cracking. This crack will, initially at least, be bridged by fibres (Figure 1a). These fibres provide support for the crack in a fashion which is analogous to the crack tip situation considered by Barenblatt (15). Unfortunately, the propagation of such cracks cannot be rigorously analysed. However, these fibres do exert a negative pressure on the crack in the region of the tip.

We will now show that an internal pressure is equivalent to a change in crack length. Murrell (16) has shown that a body under stress σ_c , with a crack having an internal (positive) pressure, P , has a strain energy release rate, dU_e/da_o , for plane strain given by

$$\frac{dU_e}{da_o} = 2\pi(1-\nu^2)(\sigma_c + P)^2 a_o/E \quad (8)$$

The corresponding strain energy release rate for a crack with a notional increase in length of r_p is

$$\frac{dU_e}{da_o} = 2\pi(1-\nu^2)(a_o + r_p)\sigma_c^2/E \quad (9)$$

These two are equal if

$$(1 + P/\sigma_c)^2 = (1 + r_p/a_o) \quad (10)$$

Clearly, using equation 10, we can calculate P if r_p is known.

To estimate the notional pressure, we will take the average pressure resulting from the linear closing of a crack (this gives a more liberal estimate than that for the Barenblatt closing).

For randomly distributed parallel fibres, the average distance that the shorter ends extend from the crack plane, at the original crack tip, when it has opened up to such an extent that work G_{fp} can be expended, is $l_c/4$. This average value is assumed to decrease linearly from the crack tip, and become zero at a distance a_m . The average fibre stress in the process zone is thus $\sigma_{fu}/4$, and contributes a total force of $V_f \sigma_{fu} a_m/4$ per unit thickness of material. The notional pressure is assumed to be exerted over the whole crack up to the end of the matrix crack. Thus it exerts a tensile force $-P(a_o + a_m)$ per unit thickness of material on each half of the crack. Thus, for the two to be equivalent

$$P = - \frac{V_f \sigma_{fu} a_m}{4(a_o + a_m)} \quad (11)$$

(A similar result is obtained from a more exact analysis using (17) for example.)

Development of a Matrix Crack in the Worked Zone

We can now use equations 8 and 11 to determine the strain energy release rate dU/da_m for matrix cracking:

$$\frac{dU}{da_m} = 2\pi(1-\nu_c^2)(\sigma_c + P)^2(a_o + a_m)/E_c \quad (12)$$

where σ_c and E_c are the appropriate elastic constants for the composite. The energy absorption rate for the matrix crack is $V_m G_m$ where G_m is the work of fracture and V_m the volume fraction of the matrix. We can find a value of a_m , a_{mc} say, for which the energy release and energy absorption rates are equal. This is the critical matrix crack length. Matrix cracks longer than this will extend indefinitely. Thus, putting dU/da_m in equation 12 equal to $V_m G_m$ and substituting a_{mc} for a_m we obtain

$$a_{mc} = \frac{V_m E_c G_m - \pi a_o \sigma_c (\sigma_c - V_f \sigma_{fu}/4)(1-\nu_c^2)}{(\sigma_c - V_f \sigma_{fu}/4)(1-\nu_c^2)} \quad (13)$$

It can be seen from this equation that there can exist a range of crack lengths, a_o , and applied stresses, σ_c , for which a_{mc} is zero. Thus the matrix

Fig. 2 Normalized plots of crack length for matrix failure for a pull-out toughening factor of ten, and crack length for composite failure, vs. applied stress.

can spontaneously crack beyond the original crack in the composite, and this crack can extend completely through the matrix, since energy release will then occur for all $a_{mc} > 0$.

Note that the condition for a_{mc} is a bounding condition. For applied stresses less than σ_{cc} (i.e. the critical value for composite failure) the crack will not open so much and the absolute value of the notional pressure will be smaller than given in equation 11.

Figure 2 shows the bounding value of a_{mc} for $G_{fp} = 10V_m G_m$, and compares the matrix fracture criterion with the composite fracture criterion. The graph has four regions:

1. For short crack lengths, and low stresses, cracks will be stable.
2. Higher stresses, and longer cracks, beyond the first curve, are accompanied by the danger of matrix cracking. The equation for this curve is

$$\sigma_c a_o (\sigma_c - V_f \sigma_{fu} / 4) = V_m G_m E_c / \pi (1 - \nu_c^2) \quad (14)$$

3. Still higher stresses and longer cracks exceed the limit for complete composite failure indicated by the second curve. This curve is governed by

Fig. 3 Normalized plots of crack length for matrix failure for a range of pull-out toughening factors (given by $G_{fp} / V_m G_m$) vs. applied stress.

the Griffith-Orowan equation (i.e. equation 2 with the appropriate values for G and the elastic constants).

4. Finally, the composite will always fail if the stress exceeds its ultimate tensile strength, σ_{CU} , which we have assumed is given with sufficient accuracy by $V_f \sigma_{fu}$. This gives a minimum value for crack length, a_{min} , where

$$a_{min} = \frac{V_m G_m E_c}{\pi(1-\nu_c^2) V_f \sigma_{fu}^2} \quad (15)$$

The graphs in Figure 2 have been plotted in dimensionless form, so that they are applicable to all composites for which $\sigma_m \approx V_f \sigma_{fu}$ and $G_{fp} = 10G_m$. This has been done by plotting the stress in the form $\sigma_c / V_f \sigma_{fu}$ and the crack length in the form a_o / a_{min} . Note that these curves are independent of any assumptions or approximations made with respect to the various elastic constants.

Figure 3 shows a similar plot for various values of $G_{fp} / V_m G_m$. It can be seen that the greater the fibre toughening, the greater the danger of matrix cracking. However, matrix cracking is only indicated for stresses greater than one quarter of the composite strength.

Conclusions

This theoretical analysis has suggested that, if composites are designed to take advantage of the toughening effects of fibre pull-out, there is a danger of complete matrix failure at stresses too small to cause crack propagation accompanied by fibre pull-out. This danger arises from the large crack openings associated with the generation of fibre pull-out work. Under these circumstances the applied stress should not be allowed to exceed one quarter of the ultimate tensile strength.

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